

Public finds in 2021: marshalling new data, managing ongoing challenges

Tuuli Kurisoo

Tallinna Ülikool, humanitaarteaduste instituut (Tallinn University, School of Humanities), Narva Rd 25, 10120 Tallinn, Estonia; tuuli.kurisoo@tlu.ee

Mari-Liis Posti

Tallinna Ülikool, arheoloogia teaduskogu (Tallinn University, Archaeological Research Collection), Rüütli 10, 10130 Tallinn, Estonia

Nele Kangert and Krista Karro

Muinsuskaitseamet (National Heritage Board), Pikk 2, 10123 Tallinn, Estonia

INTRODUCTION

This paper introduces recent public finds from Estonia (Table 1, Fig. 1), followed by a short overview on the latest developments on managing the vast amount of metal-detector finds by the National Heritage Board (hereafter MA). The majority of the finds were discovered by licensed hobby searchers and only a few by chance (Table 1, e.g. nos 134, 245). In 2021, the number of licensed hobbyists reached almost 800 individuals (in total 792), which is 161 more than last year (Kurisoo *et al.* 2021). Similarly, the volume of reported finds has never been so high as in 2021. Table 1 includes 274 records that is 45 records more than the year before (Kurisoo *et al.* 2021, table 1). The rapid growth of these numbers can be explained, at least partly, by the effects of Covid-19 pandemic. In 2020, only a few training programs were offered for interested parties and many hobbyists decided to wait for better times for handing over their findings. Both activities were fully resumed in the course of 2021.

Information about new discoveries is summarised in Table 1 that includes all finds that reached the MA in 2021 regardless of the time of the actual discovery. As in previous years, some deliberate exclusions have been made for better clarity of the data. For example, unidentified artefacts and find assemblages that originate from the 19th–20th centuries were omitted from the dataset. At the same time, it should be noted that most of the determinations (site types, artefact types and dates) are preliminary. The Estonian system relies heavily on the professional assessments of artefacts by archaeologists, but less than a quarter of the 2021 finds listed in Table 1 have been examined by experts within the time limit set by the law.

Fig. 1. Public finds that reached the MA in 2021. Administrative and settlement units, Estonian Land Board. Jn 1. 2021. aastal MA-sse jõudnud juhuleiud ja hobitsijate leiud. Haldusjaotus: Maa-amet. Map / Kaart: Martti Veldi

RESULTS

Northern parts of Estonia (Harju, Ida-Viru, Järva, Lääne-Viru, and Rapla Counties)

The majority of the finding places reported by the licensed hobby searchers are situated in the northern parts of Estonia (Table 1), mostly in Harju County (62 find spots). It should be stressed that Järva (33 find spots) and Lääne-Viru (41 find spots) Counties are now among the most visited regions by the metal detectorists (Fig. 1). The search activity in Ida-Viru (27 find spots) and Rapla County (8 find spots) is similar to the previous years. As expected, the contextual information of public finds is scarce and many artefacts are currently regarded as stray finds. There is information about several newly discovered hoards (e.g. nos 57, 69, 79, 88, 126, 160, 185). Burial grounds are well represented and there is evidence of them in every examined county (e.g. nos 6, 11, 34, 75, 77, 115, 135, 166, 210, 211). Also relatively many find assemblages seem to originate from the layers of settlement sites (e.g. nos 3, 18, 110, 116, 141, 174, 213).

The oldest artefacts from the northern parts of Estonia are three socketed axes: from Keila (no. 13), Erra (no. 67) and Seliküla (no. 134), all with the Bronze Age (1800–500 BC) date. There are several sites with the Roman Iron Age (50–450 AD) date and/or artefacts (nos 51, 57, 76, 84, 85, 113, 125, 133, 152, 158). One of the most remarkable finds among them is a cross-bar fibula from the Saka burial place (no. 85; Fig. 2). It has short, wide and high cross-bars, the bow and foot are heavily chiselled from the sides, and the leg which ends with a small knob bears traces of silver. It is one of the earliest variants of cross-bar fibulas (Almgren's type 95) (Almgren 1923, 50–51, plate V: 95) and the oldest representative of this type of brooches

found from Estonia. Presumably, the shape of these brooches was modelled on strongly profiled fibulae, and they were mainly used in the second half of the 2nd century (Hauptmann 1998, 164, fig. 4: 3) in the area between the Vistula and Oder Rivers – present-day Poland and Germany; a few have been also found in Lithuania and on the islands of the Baltic Sea (Öland, Bornholm and Gotland) (Hauptmann 1998, fig. 8). It may be assumed that the Saka fibula was imported to Viru County from the Polish territories in the Early Roman Iron Age.

Active usage of searching devices has increased the number of equal-armed brooches in recent years (e.g. Kurisoo *et al.* 2021, table 1, nos 55, 152; Rammo & Smirnova 2019, table 1 no. 18). This time, two specimens were unearthed in Järva County. Both of them seem to originate from burial places. Jalalõpe (no. 111) is an equal-armed brooch of Finnish type that can be dated to the 11th century (Kivikoski 1938, 25–26, fig. 21). Metstaguse (no. 128) is a Scandinavian-style specimen that was probably made in the 10th century (Kivikoski 1938, 13–15, fig. 2; Kivikoski 1973, fig. 674; Mägi 2020, 74, 75, fig. 7:3).

Five Late Iron Age hoards were discovered from the northern parts of Estonia. Although parts of the Vitsiku hoard (no. 90) were already found in 2019, additional coins and silver ingots were unearthed at the same find spot in 2021. This new evidence revealed that this hoard is exceptionally old and provides solid numismatic proof for the silver-based international trade in Estonia in the early 9th century (Leimus *et al.*, this volume). Also Ontika hoard (no. 79) that is dated to the 9th century is noteworthy. 9th century hoards are rare in Estonia and Ontika is the first one that can be dated to the very end of the 9th century (Leimus 2021a). Vainu (no. 88) hoard with a mid-10th century date is somewhat more common, but an important source for further numismatic studies (Leimus 2021b). The latter can be also said about Erra hoard (no. 69) that is composed of 11th century coins (Leimus 2021c). Valingu (no. 57) hoard contained fragments of penannular brooches from the 11th century and these items were likely stored as hack silver (pers. comm., Ülle Tamla, TLÜ AT).

The Final Iron Age finds are usually well represented and artefacts from the current dataset are no exception. Some of them are single stray finds (e.g. nos 12, 22, 23, 29), but the bulk of such finds seem to originate from cremation burials (e.g. nos 11, 14, 19, 28, 37, 38, 42, 123, 212) and settlement sites (e.g. nos 18, 32, 116, 141, 213). These artefacts represent mostly local types of ornaments and dress accessories such as brooches, pendants, bracelets, etc. A more notable piece is a copper alloy tooth pendant from Saula (no. 46). Such finds were common in south-western Finland, where more than 120 pendants are known (Asplund 2005; Kivisalo 2008). Similar finds have been also found from the lower reaches of the River Daugava, but in notably smaller quantities (Jonuks 2017; Kurisoo 2021, 48). Metal detectorists have discovered a few of such pendants from Estonia (Kiudsoo *et al.* 2012, 242, fig. 9; Rammo & Smirnova 2019, table 1: no. 65), but these are rare finds.

Artefacts from the Middle Ages (1200/1250–1558 AD) and from the Modern Period (1558 AD onwards) are also numerous. Most of them represent ornaments, dress accessories and small everyday items. A more noteworthy discovery was made in Äherdi (no. 215), where an odd

Fig. 2. Saka crossbar fibula (no. 85).

Jn 2. Saka kärbissölg (nr 85).

Photo / Foto: Nele Kangert

Fig. 3. Äherdi (no. 215) Wild Man.
Fig. 3. Äherdi (nr 215) metsmees.
 (AI 8461.)

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

anthropomorphic figurine was found. A closer examination revealed that the statuette depicts the Wild Man (Fig. 3), a popular mythical figure in medieval Europe. The symbology of the Wild Man is complex and context-dependant, but in broad terms it represents all that is alien and terrifying. According to E. Russow (2022), the Äherdi Wild Man may have adorned a chandelier, which was probably made in the 15th century. Also, a miniature pewter pestle from Veltsi (no. 183) can be highlighted. It is hypothesised that this specimen was actually a toy that belonged to an 18th century playhouse that mimicked the real domestic environment and came from the nearby Veltsi manor (Russow 2021a).

A small set of iron artefacts from Lümandu (no. 211; Fig. 4 B–E) refer to a smithery that was active between the 14th and 17th centuries (see more in Saage 2022). Perhaps

the most significant discovery is an iron pipe that on the basis of its form and construction would be best suited for bellows, working as the nozzle (Fig. 4: B). In addition, an iron object (Fig. 4: C), a small anvil (Fig. 4: D) with extensive use-wear traces and a piece of osmund iron (Fig. 4: E), a widely used type of iron produced in Sweden, were found.

Fig. 4. Objects related to iron metallurgy from Sürgavere (no. 268) A and Lümandu (no. 211) B–E.

Jn 4. Rauametallurgiaga seotud esemed Sürgavere (nr 268) A ja Lümandust B–E (nr 211).

Photo / Foto: Ragnar Saage

Metal-detecting has steadily increased the number of 16th–17th century hoards with peasants' jewellery sets (e.g. Kurisoo *et al.* 2020, table 1: 208, 226, 222; Kurisoo *et al.* 2021, table 1: 218, 221, Rammo & Kangert 2018, table 1: 93, Tvauri 2017). One of the most impressive hoards of this type was discovered in Vetiku (Mõdriku) (no. 185). A wide variety of silver ornaments, silver-gilt pendants, numerous beads made of glass along with a few rock crystal specimens were hidden in a tripod vessel. The hobbyist who found the hoard acted in an exemplary manner and informed the MA immediately after unearthing the upper part of the vessel. This allowed archaeologists to excavate the hoard *in situ* and make relevant additional discoveries. For example, some of the ornaments (large silver beads and necklaces made of glass beads) were hidden under the tripod pot and wrapped inside a cloth or in a second vessel (Russow, this volume). Moreover, it seemed that a special stone structure was made for supporting the vessel in the soil (Muinsuskaitseamet 2021).

Western parts of Estonia (Hiiumaa, Lääne, Pärnu, and Saare Counties)

Information about the western parts continues to be scarce when compared with the northern and southern parts of Estonia (Fig. 1). Only seven find spots were recorded in Lääne County (Table 1), but more archaeological data was documented from Pärnu County (14 find spots) than before. The search activities on the island of Saaremaa have remained similar to the previous year (26 find spots). It is also worth pointing out that three new find spots were reported from the island of Hiiumaa (nos 63, 64, 65; Fig. 1), where public finds are generally rarely reported. Although these finds cannot be attributed to any archaeological site, they still enrich the knowledge of local settlement history. Among these items, a leather belt decorated with studs from Metsaküla (no. 63), which probably belonged to the waist ornament of a Modern Period woman, can be highlighted.

Approximately half of the find places can be contextualised at this stage of research. Currently there is more information about dwelling sites (e.g. nos 145, 194, 217, 224, 226, 230, 238) than burial places (e.g. nos 147, 206, 221, 229, 236). Especially noteworthy is the Uluste (no. 206) cremation burial field that helps to fill the gap in the knowledge about the first millennia of Lääne County (Mandel 2021). The most noteworthy item from Uluste is an exceptionally large iron socketed axe with a 4th–6th century date (Mandel 2021).

Only two hoards were discovered from the western parts of Estonia. The Kirimäe (no. 144) hoard is outstanding, containing 124 coins of which most numerous are German deniers and Gotland coins from the end of the 12th century and the beginning of the 13th century (Leimus 2021d). Additionally, silver bars and different ornaments (bracelets, a finger ring, a neck ring etc.) were found. Apart from the volume and variety of the silver items, the hoard also contains a true coin rarity, a bracteate of Bishop Albert of Riga (see more Leimus & Saage, this volume). A Modern Period hoard composed of diverse jewellery was also discovered from Uulu (no. 207).

Archaeological finds with a Stone Age date are usually rare among public finds in Estonia as the majority of the artefacts are metal items found by using searching devices. Nevertheless, some hobby searchers have also noted stone, quartz or flint artefacts and handed them over to the MA. For instance, a stone axe fragment with a possible Late Neolithic date was discovered from Tammese (no. 235). The oldest metal item of this dataset was obtained from Viira (no. 240). It is an Early Bronze Age axe, which for many years was used in the household as a coat hook before it was recognised as an archaeological object (Paavel 2021).

Notably more artefacts originate from the second half of prehistory. Important new knowledge about the Final Iron Age Saaremaa, especially in terms of dressing and burial customs

will result from the Lõmala (no. 229) discovery. The hobby searcher acted responsibly and informed the MA immediately after finding pieces of 12th–13th century jewellery and fragments of a human skull. Archaeological excavations on that spot yielded a single inhumation burial of a young female, approximately 15–19 years old (Kangert & Varul 2022). She was buried with diverse ornaments of which remains of a headdress are the most remarkable (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Headdress from Lõmala (no. 229).

Jn 5. Peaehelõmalast (nr 229).

(SM 10908.)

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

Artefacts from the Middle Ages and the Modern Period are also common public finds from the western parts of Estonia. A notable piece, a decorative mount or bezant, was found from Eametsa (no. 194). The gilt silver mount was probably made in the 13th–14th century, decorated with an image of an eagle (Russow 2021b). Another mount with the same effigy was found a few years ago in Erja (see more in Russow 2021c) and it was suggested that the discussed bezants decorated a religious artefact (church textile) or a secular dress (Russow 2021b, c). Another exceptional find was unearthed from Kahtla (no. 219), where a fragment of a casting mould was found. It is the first metal mould that originates from an archaeological context and on the basis of the shape, it seems to originate from the Middle Ages (pers. comm. R. Saage, TÜ).

Southern parts of Estonia (Jõgeva, Põlva, Tartu, Valga, Viljandi and Võru Counties)

Public search activities in the southern parts of Estonia follow previously established patterns. More information is available about Jõgeva County (16 find spots) followed by Tartu County (15 find spots). Other counties are represented with less than ten find spots in Table 1: seven sites are listed Viljandi, six in Valga, five in Võru and four in Põlva Counties. Stray finds dominate in the southern parts of Estonia (e.g. nos 97, 104, 106, 191, 246, 257, 259, 264, 265, 267, 271, 274), but burial grounds are also well represented (e.g. nos 93, 95, 98, 101, 103, 258, 260, 273). Active usage of metal detectors has notably contributed to the number of hoard finds and this dataset contains information about 13 hoards (Table 1). Therefore, hoards that are discovered without using a searching device are exceptional. Only one, the Soomevere hoard (Tamla & Kiudsoo 2017), can be named from the recent years. 2021 contributed to that list from Elva municipality (no. 245) where a rather large 13th–14th century coin hoard was found during gardening work. The hoard was hidden in a Langerwehe stoneware jug and contained thousands of coins – 5899 silver bracteates mainly from the Tartu Prince-Bishopric – with a total weight close to 800 grams (Kiudsoo 2022).

Several sites from Tartu and Põlva Counties are connected to the search activities conducted in the shallow water of Lake Peipsi (e.g. nos 191, 192, 193, 248, 249, 250, 252). As in previous years, the finds gathered from these sites are mostly Early Modern and Modern period Orthodox pendants, signet rings, buttons, brooches, buckles, and other small items. It has been suggested that these artefacts may originate from sunken burial places and dwelling sites (Kurisoo *et al.* 2021, 270). In the course of the last few years, interesting finds have been gathered from Laiusevälja (no. 95). The site is multi-layered, encompassing a 19th century mill, a 16th century manor estate and a Final Iron Age burial place. In addition, some probably Early Mesolithic finds have also been unearthed from the same spot (Roio 2022). The most abundant set of finds are the grave finds: pieces of ornaments and dress accessories from the Final Iron Age.

Artefacts that originate from the first half of prehistory are rare and only four such items can be named: a Kalliküla (no. 257) flint scraper with a possible Stone Age date, a stone axe from Suislepa (no. 267) dating from the Late Neolithic to the Bronze Age, and a Late Bronze Age socketed axe from Koobassaare (no. 259). Many find assemblages contain a wide variety of artefacts that date from the Final Iron Age to the Modern Period. Most of such artefacts are small finds such as finger rings, pendants, bells, brooches, and parts of belts. Besides more common objects there are three items that deserve to be pointed out.

The first is a round openwork pendant with a face-shaped extension below the suspension loop from Marjamäe (no. 265). Anthropomorphic design is uncommon in the archaeological

record of Estonia (Kurisoo 2021, 269–270) and all items that are human-shaped or feature anthropomorphic elements such as faces stand out. The origin of this find as well as its date need some further research, but it can be speculated that this object may date from the Final Iron Age or somewhat later. The second object is a rare 13th–14th century seal from Selli (no. 103). It has a simple design (Fig. 6), depicting a coat of arms, the inscription around the rim is clear and reads S'hERMANNI DE PAI'SGELE 'seal (S = Sigillum) that belongs to Hermann from Paisgele / Pavsgelē', but the origin of the seal is still open (Russov 2021d). According to Erki Russov (2021d), the shield in the middle of the seal indicates that Hermann had a status of a vassal and he was not a member of the clergy. It is likely that the seal

Fig. 6. Seal from Selli (no. 103).

Jn 6. Selli pitsat (nr 103).

(TÜ 3018.)

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

was accidentally lost, which is indicated by the good condition of the artefact. The third object is a massive iron bloom (3.4 kg) from Sürgavere (no. 268) village. It is another iron object with a great significance for research (Fig. 3: A). According to the preliminary study conducted by S. Jegorov and R. Saage, this piece of iron was produced locally in Viljandi County as the slag inside the bloom has a similar composition to the slag found from Olustvere village, not far away from Sürgavere (Jegorov 2022).

MANAGING THE VAST AMOUNT OF PUBLICLY DISCOVERED METAL-DETECTOR FINDS

2021 marks the 10th year of legislation that regulates the use of searching devices by private persons in Estonia (HCA amendment 2011). The number of licence holders has increased by almost nine times in the past decade from 91 permit holders in 2012 (Ots & Rammo 2013, 300) to 792 in 2021 (see above). The rapid increase of metal detectorists also means that there has been a significant growth in the volume of archaeological finds and newly discovered sites. This has increased the workload of the MA: all finds need to be collected from the hobby searchers and evaluated, potential new monuments need to be studied on site, communication with finders and land owners has to be prompt and regular. Moreover, the budget that is foreseen for evaluating and conserving public finds does not cover the high amount of artefacts that is handed over to the MA. These issues are amplified by the shortage of resources, both human and technological, that support the management of public finds.

Even more worrisome is the fact that MA struggles with protecting new archaeological sites. In the past years, only a few find spots have officially allocated the status of an archaeological monument in Estonia and none of these sites were discovered by metal detecting. It is worth pointing out that the overwhelming majority of new archaeological sites have been discovered by private persons using metal detectors in the past decade. This, in turn, leads to several issues such as rediscovering the already known sites by different individuals, which inevitably damages or even destroys archaeological find contexts (see also Rammo & Kangert 2018, 214).

Despite these difficulties, there have been some positive developments that help to face the challenges. In 2021, an additional position for a heritage specialist focusing on public finds was created at the MA. Besides shared workload, also the first database that includes

exclusively information about Estonian public finds has been created. This database is one of the results of the MetDect project¹ and includes more than 40 000 artefacts with contextual information. The first version of the MetDect database is appended to the MA's internal geoportal. Thus, for the first time metal-detected artefacts compose a separate map layer that can be combined with other resources. In that respect, the MetDect database has become an essential tool not only for identifying new archaeological sites, but also for heritage-related prevention work. Moreover, this new development has great potential for speeding up and simplifying the process of assessing the cultural value of new public finds.

SUMMARISING REMARKS

The geographical distribution of the reported find spots is similar to the previous years and hobby searchers were most active in the northern parts of Estonia, especially in Harju, Järva and Lääne-Viru Counties. The western and southern parts of Estonia are either less examined by the hobbyists or the reporting is incomplete. The oldest finds introduced in this paper can be dated to the Stone Age and the Bronze Age, but they are not numerous. The bulk of the find assemblages listed in Table 1 have a wide date from the end of prehistory to the end of the modern area. This corresponds well with the results from the previous years.

The main challenges are still connected to the vast amount of public finds and a growing interest in obtaining a search permit for using metal detectors. Both of these aspects have caused a situation where the MA struggles with the influx of information and protecting new sites. However, there have been some internal (a new position at the MA) and external (MetDect database) developments that give reasons to be moderately optimistic about more efficient data management in the future.

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¹ MetDect project: Metal-detected past: a study of long-term developments in settlement patterns, technology and visual culture on the example of metal-detector finds from Estonia.

Table 1. Finds discovered by users of searching devices and stray finds reported to the National Heritage Board in 2021. Former parish name (if different from the present municipality name) is given in brackets.

Tabel 1. Otsinguvahendiga leitud ja juhuslikult avastatud leiud, mis jõudsid 2021. a Muinsuskaitseametisse. Sulgudes on esitatud kihelkond, juhul kui see erineb kehtivast haldusjaotusest.

Compiled by / Koostanud: Nele Kangert, Mari-Liis Posti, Tuuli Kurisoo, Krista Karro

C – cemetery, burial place / kalmistu, matmispaik

F – stray find / juhuleid

H – hoard, deposit find / peitleid

S – settlement site / asulakoht

HS – harbour site / sadamakoht

M – manufacturing site / tootmisega seotud muistis

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no./ Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
HARJUMAA								
1	Alansi	F	Kose	Coin pendant, waist ornament	Modern period		M. Kobets	
2	Alansi	F	Kose	Coins, chain holder	Modern Period?		V. Nezgovorov	
3	Alliku	S	Saue (Keila)	Rectangular ornament link, buckles, brooch pin, mount, rings, fragments of copper alloy items (dress pin, signet ring, belt fittings, waist ornament, burnt items), thimble, coins, buttons, iron tool fragments, tin fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Järvis	
4	Aruaru	F	Jõelähtme (Harju-Jaani)	Dress pins, pendant fragment	Late Iron Age		Anonymous	
5	Harju-Risti	F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Scale weight, pendant	Final Iron Age		H. Järvis, L. Järvis	
6	Hatu, Pae	C	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Knives, spearhead, arrow-heads, brooch pin fragment	Final Iron Age		H. Järvis, L. Järvis	
7	Hüüru	F	Saue (Keila)	Pewter pendant, metal bar	Middle Ages – Modern Period		V. Fleišman	E. Russow
8	Igavere	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Seax	Middle Ages		J. Ojabinstein	
9	Jaanika	S	Saue (Nissi)	Mount, rectangular ornament link, bells, needle, finger-ring, small round brooch, belt fitting, ring, fragments of copper alloy items (chape, bracelet, burnt items), coins, buttons, tin seal, tin bullets, thimble, nail, ear ring, tin fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Meipalu	
10	Jaanika	F	Saue (Nissi)	Mount, pendant	Late Iron Age		R. Randlane	
11	Kalesi	C, F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Bells, penannular brooches, brooch pin, trapezoid pendants, zoomorphic pendant, mounts, bracelets, waist ornaments, pewter mount, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (dress pin, buckles, finger-rings, pewter pendant, buckle detail, metal items)	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8563	Anonymous, J. Gaidai	A. Kütt, R.-M. Moon

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no./ Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
12	Kata	F	Kose	Rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age	AI 8582	Anonymous	
13	Keila	F	Keila	Bronze socketed axe	Bronze Age		Anonymous	
14	Kiia	C, F	Saue (Keila)	Dress pins, bells, pendants, rectangular ornament link, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (penannular brooches, bracelets, burnt fragments), mount	Viking Age – Middle Ages	AI 8581	Anonymous	
15	Kopli	F	Rae (Jüri)	Penannular brooch, brooch pin, bracelet fragment, metal items	Final Iron Age	AI 8587	Anonymous	
16	Koppelmaa	F	Saue (Keila)	Belt mounts	Final Iron Age	AI 8528	A. Sudovykh	H. Luik
17	Kõmmaste	C, F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Mounts, finger-ring, rectangular ornament link, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (dress pin, brooch), pewter fragment, scale weight, book clasp, burnt items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Järvis, L. Järvis	
18	Kõmmaste	S?	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Scale weights, mounts, trapezoid pendant, tweezers, round brooch, ring, rectangular ornament link, fastening plate, fragments of copper alloy items, knife fragment, ice nail	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		H. Järvis	
19	Kõmmaste	C, F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Buckle, mounts, tripod pot fragment, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (brooch, pin, finger-ring), burnt items	Final Iron Age, Middle Ages		H. Järvis	
20	Lehetu	F	Saue (Nissi)	Cruciform pendant fragment, rivet, copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
21	Lehetu	F	Saue (Nissi)	Fastening plate	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
22	Lehola	F	Lääne-Harju (Keila)	Scale weight	Final Iron Age		E. Klaas	
23	Madila	F	Saue (Nissi)	Axe-shaped pendant	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
24	Madise	F	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Brooch fragment	Viking Age		E. Klaas	
25	Metslõugu	F	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Silver coin, copper alloy item	Middle Ages		A. Morozov	
26	Määra	C?	Lääne-Harju (Harju-Madise)	Fragment of penannular brooch, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	
27	Nurme	S	Saue (Nissi)	Silver coin, nail, bell	Middle Ages		H. Järvis	
28	Nurme	C, S	Saue (Nissi)	Mounts, rectangular ornament links, silver coin, penannular brooches, pin, bead, belt separator, buckle, fastening plates, finger-ring, signet ring, fragments of copper alloy items (mount, burnt items)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
29	Nurme	F	Saue (Nissi)	Fragment of zoomorphic pendant	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	

No. / Site / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no. / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
30	Nurme	C?	Saue (Nissi)	Fragment of knife sheath, scale weight, silver coin, bells, brooch pin, dress pin?, pendant fragments, ring	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	
31	Oru	F	Kose	Finger-ring	Middle Ages?		Anonymous	
32	Pae	S	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Brooch pin, mount, pewter bullet, fragments of copper alloy items, coin, knife handle ring	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Järvis, L. Järvis	
33	Pae	S	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Mount, waist ornament, signet ring, cruciform pendant fragment, silver coin?, pendant?	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Järvis, L. Järvis	
34	Pae	C	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Push-key spring lock, scale weights, signet ring, nails, mounts, rivets, rectangular ornament links, pendants, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, chains, brooch pin, dress pins) and burnt items, axes, knives, spearhead, javelin head, sword cross-guard, sword scabbard chape, bridle details, coin pendant, knife sheath elements, scythe, fragments of iron items (buckles, bell, mounts, nails, rivets, spur)	Final Iron Age		H. Järvis	
35	Pae	C	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Brooch pin, pendant fragment	Final Iron Age		H. Järvis	
36	Pala	C	Kose	Chain holder, mounts, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (dress pins, fastening plate, brooch pins)	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
37	Pala	C, F	Kose	Pendant, bronze bead, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, chains), burnt fragments of copper alloy items, slag, fragment of cruciform pendant?	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous, V. Tkatchuk	
38	Partsaare	C, F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Pendants, chain holder, bell, mounts, knife handle detail, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelet, chain, dress pin)	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
39	Patika	F	Rae (Jüri)	Fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	A. Kütt
40	Peningi	F	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Pendant fragment, bell, penannular brooch fragment	Final Iron Age	AI 8578, AI 8579	Anonymous	
41	Püha	C? F	Saue (Keila)	Buckle, book clasp	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Findings / Leitud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no. / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
42	Raveliku	C, S	Kose	Glass beads, coins, fragments of coins, mounts, bells, finger-rings, pin of penannular brooch, signet rings, rectangular ornament links, fragments of copper alloy items (waist ornament, penannular brooch, bracelets, chain holder, central plaque, neck ring, pendants, burnt items), buttons, pottery, rings, pewter items, pewter mount	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Agurauja, J. Gaidai	R.-M. Moon
43	Raveliku	S?	Kose	Coin, fastening plate, pendant, finger-ring, knife handle detail, fragments of copper alloy items (brooch pins, chain, other items), kettle hook fragment	Middle Ages		A. Agurauja	
44	Salu	F	Rae (Harju-Jaani)	Pewter pendant	15th c	AI 8573	Anonymous	E. Russow
45	Salu	C?, S?	Rae (Harju-Jaani)	Silver coins, bell, pendant, chain distributor, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
46	Saula	C? S?	Kose	Bracelets, bells, mount, pewter pendant, copper alloy tooth pendant, fragments of jewellery (e.g. brooches)	Final Iron Age	AI 8571, AI 8575	Anonymous	A. Kütt
47	Saula	S	Kose	Signet ring, ornament link	Early Modern Period		J. Gaidai	R.-M. Moon
48	Saunja	S?	Kuusalu (Jõelähtme)	Pendant, finger-rings	Viking Age, Middle Ages		A. Ksentsov	
49	Soodla	F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Crossbow fibula, belt distributor	Migration Period		Anonymous	
50	Tammiku	C	Kose	Mounts, spiral tubes, silver coin fragment, bell, pendant, ornament link, fastening plate, scabbard chape, fragments of copper alloy items (dress pins, bracelets), metal fragment	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8576, AI 8577	Anonymous, J. Kolistratova	A. Kütt, A. Unt
51	Tõhelgi	C	Raasiku (Harju-Jaani)	Crossbow fibula fragment, penannular brooch fragment, bracelet fragment	Roman Iron Age, Late Iron Age	AI 8580	J. Tkatchenko, Anonymous	
52	Vaidasoo	S	Rae (Jüri)	Fastening plate, bell, finger-rings, mounts, lock, spur fragment, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (chain holder, penannular brooch, brooch pin)	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	A. Kütt
53	Vaidasoo	F	Rae (Jüri)	Knife, bell	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8568	Anonymous	
54	Vaidasoo	F	Rae (Jüri)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age	AI 8586	Anonymous	
55	Valgejõe	F	Kuusalu (Haljala)	Elements of waist ornament	Modern period		K. Kasemets	M. Niinesalu
56	Valgejõe	F	Kuusalu (Haljala)	Spur, spearhead, tin bullets	Modern period		A. Alaküla	

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57	Valingu	H, C	Saue (Keila)	Silver penannular brooch fragments, copper alloy penannular brooch, mount, shield-headed fibula fragments, coins, metal items	Roman Iron Age – Late Iron Age	AI 8616	Anonymous, K. Koppe	
58	Vaskjala	F	Rae (Jüri)	Rectangular ornament link, fragment of neck ring, waist ornament, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Tkatchenko	
59	Võlle	S?	Kose	Chain distributor, fastening plate, bracelet fragment, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age	AI 8564	Anonymous	
60	Üksnurme	F	Saku (Keila)	Coin	11th c		Anonymous	
61	Üksnurme	S	Saku (Keila)	Bird-shaped pendant, chain link with ring, fragment of scabbard chape, coin	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
62	Ülgase	F?, C?	Jõelähtme	Penannular brooch, round brooches, heart-shaped brooch, brooch pin, finger-rings, rectangular ornament link, fragment of silver finger-ring, fragment of pendant, fragment of silver coin	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Mljavov	
HIIMUMAA								
63	Metsaküla	F	Hiiumaa (Reigi)	Fragments of leather belt with mounts and fastening plate	Modern Period		I. Salusoo	
64	Partsi	F	Hiiumaa (Pühalepa)	Mount	Middle Ages – Modern Period		I. Salusoo	
65	Pühalepa-Harju	F	Hiiumaa (Pühalepa)	Rectangular ornament link, bell	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Salusoo	
IDA-VIRUMAA								
66	Aa	S?	Lüganuse	Iron socketed axe, penannular brooch, finger-ring, belt fitting	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		A. Kotkin, A. Smirnov	
67	Erra	S, F	Lüganuse	Bronze socketed axe, pendant, bridle boss, bell, penannular brooch, bracelet fragment, fragments of metal items	Late Bronze Age, Final Iron Age – Middle Ages	AI 8478	E. Kessel	K. Paavel
68	Erra	S? F	Lüganuse	Signet ring, finger-ring, bead, brooch fragment, fragment of copper alloy item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		J. Tkatchenko	
69	Erra	H	Lüganuse	Silver coins and fragments	11th c	AI 8558	J. Tkatchenko	I. Leimus
70	Erra-Liiva	C, S, F	Lüganuse	Crossbow fibula, bell, fragments of copper alloy items, pendant, bell, coin, signet ring, book clasp, metal item	Migration Period, Final Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Tkatchenko	
71	Erra-Liiva	F	Lüganuse	Fragment of bracelet, fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age		J. Tkatchenko	

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72	Kahula	F	Jõhvi	Spearhead	Middle Ages – Modern Period?		I. Novitski	
73	Koljala	C?	Lüganuse	Cross-bar fibula, scabbard chape, pendant, fragment of copper alloy item	Roman Iron Age – Final Iron Age		J. Tkatshenko	
74	Konju	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Brooch, mounts, knife handle detail	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		S. Zaitsev	
75	Matka	C, F	Lüganuse	Fire-steels, finger-ring, zoomorphic and trapezoid pendants, book clasp, fragment of dirham, frag- ments of copper alloy items (bracelet, brooch), handle, metal item	Viking Age – Modern Period		J. Tkatshenko	
76	Matka	C, F	Lüganuse	Crossbow fibula, lunula pendant, bracelet, head- shield fibula, cross-bar fib- ula, finger-rings, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (e.g. bracelets), metal items, mount	Roman Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Tkatshenko	
77	Mäetaguse	C	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Axe, anvil, fragment of sword with cross-guard, pommel, spearheads, fragments of knives, candlestick, bridle bits, chain holders, fragments of copper alloy items (buckles, bracelets, burnt items), fragments of iron items, scythe?, bell	Late Iron Age		Anonymous	
78	Ohakvere	H?	Alutaguse (Jõhvi)	Fragments of silver sheet pendants	Modern Period		S. Zaitsev	
79	Ontika	H	Toila (Jõhvi)	Dirhams	9th c		D. Šutov	I. Leimus
80	Pauliku	F	Jõhvi	Dirham	Viking Age		S. Andrejev	
81	Peeri	F	Toila (Jõhvi)	Fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	
82	Puhkova	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Trapezoid pendant	Modern Period?		A. Balkanski	A. Kütt
83	Saka	S?	Toila (Lüganuse)	Scythe fragments, knives, fragments of knife, arrow head/ spearhead, ring with fastening plate	Migration Period, Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	
84	Saka	F	Toila (Lüganuse)	Pendant	Roman Iron Age		E. Kessel	
85	Saka	C	Toila (Lüganuse)	Cross-bar fibula, fragment of bracelet, burnt fragment	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	M.-L. Posti, Ü. Tamla
86	Soldina	S	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Spur detail, ear ring/ tem- ple ornament?	Modern Period?		N. Galimov	
87	Soldina	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Cruciform pendant	Final Iron Age		I. Novitski	
88	Vainu	H	Lüganuse	Dirhams	10th c	AI 8555	J. Tkatshenko	I. Leimus
89	Vainu	C?, S	Lüganuse	Axes, scabbard chape, tweezers, temple ornament, knife sheath, fragment of metal item	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		J. Tkatshenko, A. Smirnov	I. Leimus
90	Vitsiku	H	Toila (Jõhvi)	Dirhams and fragments, silver ingots, fragments of copper alloy items	Viking Age		E. Kessel	I. Leimus

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91	Voorepera	F	Lüganuse	Coin, fragment of copper alloy item	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		E. Kessel	
92	Vodava	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Silver coin, bracelet	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Tšumakov	
JÕGEVAMAA								
93	Alavere	C, S	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Mounts, fragments of copper alloy bracelets, burnt items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Pärtelpoeg	
94	Jõgeva alevik	S, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Detail of waist ornament, coin pendant, fragments of copper alloy jewellery, burnt items	Modern Period		T. Sei	
95	Laiusevälja	C, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Bells, finger-rings, mounts, fastening plate, scale weights, rectangular ornament link, ring, key, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (bracelets, chains, burnt items), fragments of iron items, bullets, pewter items, nails, iron tool fragment, metal items, coins, grinding stone	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		E. Pärtelpoeg	
96	Lebavere	S?, F	Põltsamaa	Signet ring, finger-rings, bell, penannular brooch fragment	Middle Ages		Anonymous	
97	Mõhküla	F	Põltsamaa	Knife handle detail	Modern Period		M. Paabort	E. Russow
98	Palupere	C, F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Mounts, rectangular ornament link, bells, finger-rings, coins, push-key spring lock?, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (brooches, brooch pins, bracelets), burnt items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
99	Patjala	S?	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Pendants, signet ring, fragment of coin	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
100	Selli	C, S?	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Coins, coin pendant, button, mounts, tweezers, fragment of pendant, fragments of copper alloy items, fragment of pewter mount, slag	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov
101	Selli	C, F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Bells, coin pendants, pendants, needle fragment, penannular brooches, rectangular ornament links, coins, scale weight, knife and knife fragment, fragments of copper alloy items (round brooch, dress pins, bracelets, signet ring, mounts, burnt items), buckle pin, fastening plate, pewter mount, pewter items, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov

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102 Selli	C?, F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Ornament link, mount, pendant, coin pendant, bells, coins, belt end, fragments of copper alloy items (bracelets, chain holder, bell, burnt item), fastening plate, pewter mount fragment, waist ornament, metal items, tooth	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov
103 Selli	C, F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Seal, scale weight, ice nails, bell, pendants, cruciform pendant, buckles, mounts, pewter item, silver coins, coin pendants, sheet pendant, rectangular ornament link, bells, bracelets, signet rings, finger-rings, fragment of chain, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (e.g. dress pin, brooch, burnt items), knife, spearheads, nails, padlocks, keys, buckle, ox shoe, casting mould, pewter items, whistle, pipe bowl, fragments of iron items (knives, scissors, etc.), pottery, padlock, fragment of kettle, fragment of bottle, pewter mount, tobacco pipe cleaner	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	TÜ 3018	P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov, E. Russow
104 Tooma	F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Seax	Late Iron Age?		V. Rumyantsev	
105 Tõivere	C? F	Põltsamaa	Pendant, bell, mount, pewter mount, fragments of copper alloy and pewter items	Modern Period		J. Naaber	
106 Vilina	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Scale weight	Modern Period?		T. Sei	
107 Vägeva	S, C?	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Detail of waist ornament, penannular brooch fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov
108 Änkküla	C	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Fragment of copper alloy jewellery (neck ring, bracelets, pendants, tripod pot, other items), fragment of silver coin	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Naaber, K. Keske	
JÄRVAMAA							
109 Ageri	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		H. Vaalundi	
110 Ammuta	S, F	Järva (Peetri)	Bells, ice nail, tweezers, small round brooch, fragments of copper alloy items (cross-bar fibula, bracelets, chain holder, buckles, other items), buttons, coins, coin pendant, belt fittings, thimble, pewter items, metal items	Roman Iron Age, Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	

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111	Jalalõpe	C, S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Equal-armed brooch, round brooches, bells, fastening plates, rectangular ornament link, buckle, fragments of tripod pot, ice nail, mounts, coin pendants, silver coins, silver item fragments (e.g. bead), pendants, signet rings, finger-rings, hook, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. penannular brooches, bracelets, burnt items), pewter mounts, tin seal, details of waist ornament, thimble, book clasp, axe, metal items	Viking Age – Modern Period	AI 8527	H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	H. Luik, A. Kütt, M. Niinesalu
112	Jalametsa	F	Järva (Pilistvere)	Bell, chain holder fragment	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		V. Fleišman	M. Niinesalu
113	Jalgsema	S, F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Stylus, mounts, silver coin, fastening plates, rectangular ornament links, finger-rings, signet ring, penannular brooches, round brooch, brooch pins, bead, bells, pendants, bell with chain and chain holder fragment, coin pendants, scabbard chape, details of waist ornament, buckles, tobacco pipe cleaner, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. comb-shaped pendant, chain holder, bracelets, chains, cruciform pendant, burnt items), pewter mount, iron fragment, pewter items, button	Roman Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	M. Niinesalu
114	Jõgisoo	C?	Järva (Ambla)	Fastening plate, pendant, finger-ring	Final Iron Age	AI 8572	Anonymous, Anonymous	
115	Kaalepi	C, F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Finger-rings, bells, pendants, dress pins, bracelets, ring, fastening plate, fragments of copper alloy items, fragment of iron item, pewter plaque, fragments of pewter items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Suve	
116	Kaaruka	S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Bell, fragment of copper alloy items (penannular brooch, mount, pendant, bracelet, other burnt items), pewter mount	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		Anonymous	MKA
117	Kaaruka	F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Fragment of bracelet	Late Iron Age		E. Promm	S. Jegorov

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118	Kagavere	C, S, F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Drill pit?, mace head, bells, coin pendants, coins, dirham, mounts, buckles, knife pendant, penannular and small round brooches, small round brooches, brooch pins, cruciform pendants, pendants, scale weight, finger-rings, signet rings, spiral tube, needle, seal matrix, ring, rectangular ornament links, brooch pin, pin, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. fastening plate, dress pins, belt fitting, bracelets, zoomorphic pendant, scabbard chape, key, burnt items), detail of waist ornament, ice nail, book clasps, fitting plate, pewter mounts, items and fragments, glass bead, pewter pendants, rectangular iron item, iron bar fragment, spindle whorl, pottery, seal matrix	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8520, AI 8521, AI 8522, AI 8523	H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	H. Luik, M. Niinesalu, A. Kütt
119	Kukevere	C?	Järva (Ambla)	Fragments of comb-shaped pendant, S-shaped pendant, buckles, knife sheath, coins, button, pewter button?	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		Anonymous	
120	Kuksema	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bird-shaped pendant, pendants, pewter pendant, penannular brooches, bells, strap end, belt separator, fragments of copper alloy items (bracelet, dress pin head, round brooch, bell, burnt items), fragment of spearhead/ iron tool, mounts, buckle, pewter mount	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8525	H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	H. Luik, M. Niinesalu
121	Kuksema	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bells, penannular brooch pin, lead seal, fragment of copper alloy items	Middle Ages – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	A. Kütt, M. Niinesalu
122	Kuksema	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bells, coins, fragment of silver item	Middle Ages – ?		H. Vaalundi	M. Niinesalu
123	Kurisoo	C?	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Scale weight, bells, fragments of copper alloy items (bracelet, dress pin, pendant, burnt items), flint	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Suve	A. Kütt
124	Lehtmetsa	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Fragment of finger-ring	Iron Age		Anonymous	

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125	Metsla	S	Järva (Koeru)	Trapezoid pendants, bells, buckle, mount, belt separator with fastening plate, silver bead, coins, pendant, S-shaped pendant with S-shaped link, pewter pendant, penannular brooches, brooch pins, finger rings, signet ring, fragments of copper alloy items (head-shield fibula, round brooch, dress pins, chains, bracelets, fastening plate, spiral tube, cruciform pendant, burnt items), axe, lock fragment, pewter mount	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Suve, H. Vaalundi	M. Niinesalu
126	Metsla	H	Järva (Koeru)	Silver beads, sheet pendants	Early Modern Period	AI 8583	Anonymous	
127	Metstaguse	F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Penannular brooch fragment	Final Iron Age		H. Vaalundi	H. Luik
128	Metstaguse	C, F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Pendant, bells, signet ring, fragment of equal-armed brooch, fragment of neck ring with mushroom-shaped ends, fragment of pewter item, knife	Iron Age, Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	M. Niinesalu
129	Mägise	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Fragment of penannular brooch	Middle Ages		M. Suve	
130	Mäo	S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Fragments of arquebus, axes, mace head tools?, S-shaped pendant, penannular brooch, bells, buckle, buckle pin, coins, tin bullets, fragments of copper alloy and tin items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8612	R. Lallu	
131	Orgmetsa	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Fragment of cruciform pendant and finger-ring	Final Iron Age		E. Promm	
132	Ramma	S	Järva (Koeru)	Spearhead, cruciform pendants, orthodox cruciform pendant, penannular brooches, fastening plate with S-shaped link, bells, signet rings, details of waist ornament, knife, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. pendant, sheet pendant, burnt item), tin mounts, fragments of tin ornaments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	M. Niinesalu
133	Seidla, Kaalepi	C, F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Eye-fibula, rectangular ornament links, S-shaped link, mount, bells, belt separator, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (crossbow fibulae, dress pin, bracelets, finger-rings, burnt items), metal items	Roman Iron Age – Late Iron Age		A. Vares, E. Promm	
134	Seliküla	F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bronze socketed axe	Late Bronze Age	AI 8477	R. Talkis	K. Paavel

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135 Seliküla	C, F	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Finger-ring, mounts, coins, fragments of copper alloy items (dress pin, penannular brooch, pendant, cruciform pendant, other items), tin pendant, tin seal, pewter mounts	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	M. Niinesalu
136 Seliküla	C, S?	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Scale weight, buckle, fastening plates, bell, coin, coin pendants, mounts, rectangular ornament links, finger-rings, ornament link, fragments of copper alloy items (fragment of zoomorphic crossbow brooch, round brooch, finger ring with volute, bracelets, chain holder, chains, pendants, penannular brooches, tobacco pipe cleaner, bracelets, burnt items), thimble, coins, knife, scythe fragment, iron tool fragments, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8519	H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	M. Niinesalu, H. Luik
137 Säasküla	C, F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Cruciform pendants, dress pin, coin, mounts, bells, signet ring, brooch pin fragment, fragment of bracelets, signet ring and other burnt items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
138 Valasti	S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Finger-ring, fragment of cruciform pendant, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8526	H. Vaalundi	H. Luik
139 Valasti	C, S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Coin pendant, bells, silver bead, knife-shaped pendant, rectangular ornament link, belt fittings, chain separator, cruciform pendants, mounts, pewter mount, finger-rings, rings, chain link, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. penannular brooches, bracelets, waist ornaments, burnt items), seal matrix, knife, buckle pin, bullets, buttons, thimble, book clasp, pipe cover, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Promm, A. Vares	A. Kütt, M. Niinesalu
140 Viisu	C?, F	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Finger-ring with volute, bells, fragments of bracelets, fragment on penannular brooch	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
141 Öötlä	S	Järva (Peetri)	Axe, ice nail, knife fragment, brooch pin, horse/ ox shoe?, nail, bells, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooches, pendants, bells, belt fitting), buckle, buttons, coins, bullet, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		R. Lallu, A. Piirsalu	

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LÄÄNEMAA								
142	Ehmja	C	Lääne-Nigula (Martna)	Chain holder, mount	Viking Age	AI 8460	A. Sidorov	K. Ilves
143	Jõgisoo	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Medallion	Modern Period		J. Ojabstein	
144	Kirimäe	H	Lääne-Nigula	Fragments of silver bracelets, neck ring, silver ingots	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	I. Leimus
145	Kirimäe	S	Lääne-Nigula	Fragment of crossbow fibula, brooch pins, coin pendant, books clasp, fragments of copper alloy items (buckle, belt fitting), fragment of coin	Migration Period – Modern Period		Anonymous	
146	Kuijõe	F	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Bell, dress pin fragment	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
147	Liivi	C	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Scale weight, coin, mounts, fragments of jewellery (silver finger-ring, copper alloy items), bullets, buttons, coins, keys, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Ojabstein	
148	Uugla	F	Lääne-Nigula	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age		I. Ojakäär	
LÄÄNE-VIRUMAA								
149	Aasu	C, F	Haljala	Eye-fibula, silver crossbow fibula fragment, chain holder, fragments of copper alloy items (dress pin, bracelets, chain, bracelet, mount, burnt items), ring	Roman Iron Age – Viking Age?		J. Ojabstein	
150	Ebavere	F	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooch fragment	Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
151	Eipri	F	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age		L. Roots	
152	Iila	C	Viru-Nigula	Pendant fragment	Roman Iron Age		A. Timm	
153	Iila	S	Viru-Nigula	Pendant, brooch pin, belt fitting, scale weight, pendant of St Anthony cross, round pendant with Calvary motif, fastening plate	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Timm	
154	Iila	F	Viru-Nigula	Finger-ring, fragment of finger-ring, fragments of dirhams	Viking Age – Modern Period		A. Timm	
155	Imastu	C?	Tapa (Kadrina)	Fragment of dress pin, book clasp, ornament link	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
156	Jootme	C	Tapa (Ambla)	Mounts, buckle, fastening plates, rings, tin pendants	Final Iron Age		I. Mljavov	
157	Kamariku	F	Väike-Maarja	Pendant, coin pendant, tin pendant	Middle Ages – Modern Period		L. Roots	
158	Karepera	F	Haljala	Pendant fragment	Roman Iron Age		I. Mokrik	
159	Kiltsi	S, F	Väike-Maarja	Round sheet pendant and fragment, small round brooch, trapezoid pendant, bell, pin of penannular brooch, book clasp, fragments of copper alloy items (cruciform pendant, burnt items), fragments of tin items	Modern Period		K. Ringo	

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160	Koluvere	H, F	Väike-Maarja (Simuna)	Round sheet pendants, fragments of bracelet	Roman Iron Age, Middle Ages?		Anonymous	
161	Kuru	C, F	Tapa (Ambla)	Penannular brooch fragments, fire-steel, buckle, pendant, signet ring, mounts, buckle, brooch pin, pewter mount, pewter pendants, spiral tube, fragments of burnt copper alloy items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
162	Linnape	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Fragment of waist ornament, fragment of pendant, mount	Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
163	Linnape	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Fragment of dress pin, fragment of cruciform pendant, fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
164	Läpi	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Fragment of dress pin, fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
165	Malla	F	Viru-Nigula	Finger-ring, pendant	Middle Ages		A. Timm	
166	Müüriku	C, S	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooch, small round brooch, bells, pendants, signet ring, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (dress pin, pendant)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	
167	Ojakiila	F	Viru-Nigula	Fragment of bird-shaped pendant	Final Iron Age		I. Mokrik	
168	Patika	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Bell, fragment of penannular brooch, fragments of copper alloy items, pewter mount	Modern Period	AI 8570	Anonymous	
169	Pehka	F	Haljala	Tweezer pendant, penannular brooch fragment	Migration Period, Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous, A. Timm	
170	Piibe	F	Väike-Maarja (Koeru)	Arrow head	Viking Age, Final Iron Age?		P. Laidre	S. Jegorov
171	Pruuna	C, S	Tapa (Ambla)	Coins, bells, signet rings, fragments of copper alloy items (comb-shaped pendant, bracelet, penannular brooch), tin pendant	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
172	Pruuna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Waist ornament, scale weight?, ornament link	Modern Period		Anonymous	
173	Pruuna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Chain holder fragments	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
174	Rägavere	S	Tapa (Ambla)	Small round brooch, bells, fastening plate, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooch, buckle), pewter mount, mace head	Late Iron Age – Modern Period	AI 8569	Anonymous	
175	Räitsvere	F	Väike-Maarja	Pendant of St Anthony cross fragments	Modern Period		J. Potman	
176	Räsna	S	Tapa (Ambla)	Penannular brooch, belt separator, mount, lock, bells with buckle, chain fragments of copper alloy items (mounts, cruciform pendant, bracelet), knife handle detail	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	

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177	Salatse	F	Haljala	Fragment of penannular brooch, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
178	Tammiku	C, S	Väike-Maarja (Simuna)	Bell, mount, ornament link, finger-ring, penannular brooch pins, penannular brooch fragment, bracelet fragment	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Tedre, J. Potman	
179	Tõörakõrve	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Trapezoid pendant, needle case	Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
180	Vao	F	Väike-Maarja	Finger-ring	Modern Period		L. Roots	
181	Varangu	S	Väike-Maarja (Koeru)	Small round brooches, bells, finger-ring, belt fittings, buttons, coins, coin pendants, buckle, mounts, pipe cover, fragments of copper alloy items (sheet pendant, bracelet, belt separator, chain link, cover of a pipe, cruciform pendant, pendant of St Anthony cross, buckle, cockrel figurine), metal items	Modern Period		Anonymous	
182	Vasta	S?	Viru-Nigula	Rectangular ornament link, pewter mount, pewter pendant fragment	Final Iron Age		A. Svobodin	A. Kütt
183	Veltsi	F	Rakvere (Haljala)	Pewter pestle	Modern Period	AI 8471	Anonymous	E. Russow
184	Vetiku	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Spiral ring, coin pendant, fragment of buckle, small tube/ bead	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Smirnov	R.-M. Moon
185	Vetiku (Mõdriku)	H	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Tripod pot, beads, round sheet pendants, pendant of St Anthony cross, pendants, coin pendants, glass beads, coral beads, mounts, buttons, rectangular ornament link, spiral tubes, fragments of pewter jug	16th c	AI 8554	T. Vaide	E. Russow
186	Vistla	F	Tapa (Väike-Maarja)	Pendant of St Anthony cross	Modern Period		L. Roots	
187	Võhmuta	C, F	Tapa (Järva-Jaani)	Spiral tubes, fragments of jewellery (dress pin, bracelet, mount, chain holder, brooch pin, signet ring), burnt metal items, pewter seal, bullet, button	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		K. Arukaev	A. Kütt
188	Äntu	F	Väike-Maarja	Spiral ring, signet ring, silver coin	Middle Ages		L. Roots	
189	Ärina	C?, S, F	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooches, ornament link, mount, dirhams, buckle, small round brooch, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (pendant, dress pins)	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		L. Roots	MKA

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PÕLVAMAA								
190	Jõgeharä	S	Kanepi	Pendant, signet ring, tin seal, fragment of copper alloy item	Late Iron Age – Modern Period?		Anonymous	
191	Meerapalu	F	Räpina	Rhombus sheet pendant, book clasp	Middle Ages – Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
192	Meerapalu	C, S, F	Räpina	Finger-rings, signet rings, round brooch, coins, fragments of coins, coin pendants, tin bullets, buttons, buckles, ring, fragments of copper alloy items, ard point, slag	Modern Period		S. Kirsä	
193	Pedaspää	C, S, F	Räpina (Võnnu)	Round brooch, brooch pins, small round brooches, coins, coin pendants, finger-rings, signet rings, bells, bead, cruciform pendants, orthodox pendants, mounts, buckles, temple ornament, penannular brooches, nails, lock, fragments of copper alloy items (bracelets, penannular brooch, bells), knife, button, tin pendant, tin fragments, bone items	Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
PÄRNUMAA								
194	Eametsa	S	Tori (Uulu)	Bezant, coins, silver finger-ring, brooch pin, silver item fragments, lion head figurine, pendant, flint, rectangular ornament link, small sound brooch, buckle, ring, drill pit?	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Arukask, M. Puuram, Anonymous	E. Russow
195	Kaelase	S	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Fragments of silver finger-ring, brooch pin fragment, tin seal	Modern Period		A. Ankru	
196	Koonga	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Mihkli)	Mount, bell, coin, copper alloy item	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Ankru	
197	Lehu	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Coins, coin pendants, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Piirsalu	
198	Lodja	F	Saarde	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age		T. Malva	
199	Lodja	F	Saarde	Spear head, signet ring	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		T. Malva	
200	Mihkli	S	Lääneranna (Mihkli)	Small round brooch, pottery, charcoal, bones	Modern Period		L. Linder	
201	Naartse	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Mount, pewter fastening plate, finger-ring, fragments of bell, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Ankru	
202	Samliku	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Vändra)	Penannular brooch, small round brooches, bell	Modern Period		P. Maanus	
203	Soeva	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Audru)	Hen figurine fragment	Modern Period		A. Ankru	

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204	Sääre	F	Kihnu (Tõstamaa)	Coins, button	Middle Ages – Modern Period		Anonymous	I. Leimus
205	Tammiste	F	Tori (Uulu)	Penannular brooch fragments	Viking Age		M. Belikov	R.-M. Moon
206	Uluste	C	Lääneranna (Kirbla)	Mount, châtelaïne chain, pendant fragment, iron socketed axe, pommel, spiral finger-ring, penannular brooch fragment, metal item	Roman Iron Age – Late Iron Age		Anonymous	M. Mandel
207	Uulu	H	Häädemeeste (Uulu)	Finger-ring, coin pendants, coin pendant fragments, glass beads, textile fragments, leather fragments	Modern Period		H. Ööpik	

RAPLAMAA

208	Adila	F	Kohila (Hageri)	Head of dress pin	Final Iron Age		I. Krause	
209	Kohatu	C, F	Märjamaa	Comb-shaped pendant, mounts, bells, fastening plates, belt separators, rectangular ornament links, spiral tube, chape, penannular brooch pin, heart-shaped brooch, coins, finger-rings, buckle, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooches, bracelets, chains, brooch pin, burnt items), pewter mounts, book clasp	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Mljavov, V. Pratiškin	
210	Laukna	C, F	Märjamaa (Kullamaa)	Pin of penannular brooch, fastening plate, tin seal, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooches, bell, pendants, mount, fastening plates, chain links, finger-rings, burnt items)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Ankru	
211	Lümandu	C, S, M	Märjamaa	Anvil, iron items, nozzle, osmund iron, mounts, buckle with zoomorphic fastening plate, buckle, bell, coin, scythes, knife, fastening plates, bead, fragments of copper alloy items (bracelet, penannular brooches, finger-ring, dress pin, rectangular ornament links, chains, chain separators, burnt items), iron S-shaped link, knife sheath, iron items	Final Iron Age		A. Skröpnik, T. Hiob	
212	Purga	C, F	Märjamaa	Buckles, zoomorphic fastening plates, knife, fragment of tin seal, mounts, small round brooch, book clasp, ornament link, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. bracelet, finger-ring, chains, burnt items, other items)	Final Iron Age – AI 8472 Modern Period		A. Skröpnik	E. Russow

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213 Purila	S	Rapla (Juuru)	Rectangular ornament link, needle case, fragment of thimble, fragments of copper alloy items (small round brooch, finger-ring, chain, pendant)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		K. Kõiv	
214 Vankse	F	Rapla (Juuru)	Rectangular ornament link, bell, fire-steel, brooch pin, fragment of tobacco pipe cleaner, fragment of tripod pot, burnt fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		R. Paas	
215 Äherdi	F	Rapla	Anthropomorphic figurine	15th c	AI 8461	A. Sidorov	E. Russow
SAAREMAA							
216 Anseküla	F	Saaremaa (Anseküla)	Fragment of silver finger-ring, coin	Middle Ages		Anonymous	
217 Irase	S	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Coin, finger-ring fragment, pewter seal, book clasp	Middle Ages – Modern Period		T. Tohv	
218 Jõgela	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		K. Laane	
219 Kahtla	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Fragment of casting mould	Middle Ages		R. Koit	
220 Kalju	F	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age		R. Koit	
221 Kehila	C, S, F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Lunula pendant, rectangular ornament link, scale weight, neck ring fragment, bracelet fragment, coins, button, iron fragments	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		Anonymous	
222 Kogula	F	Saaremaa (Kärla)	Finger-ring	Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	
223 Kotsma	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Buckle, dress pin fragment	Late Iron Age		K. Laane	
224 Kurevere	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Belt end fragment, coin, decorative rivet, burnt item	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		Anonymous	
225 Kõruse	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Fragment of decorative element	Modern Period		E. Kessel	
226 Leedri	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Mount fragment, finger-rings, buckle, rectangular ornament link, brooch pin, coin pendant	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Tohv, K. Laane	
227 Leedri	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Bracteate, buckle, button, pendant, coin, rectangular ornament link with round chain links, chain separator, scabbard chape, metal item	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Tohv, K. Laane	
228 Lõetsa	F	Saaremaa (Muhu)	Knife, pendant, finger-ring fragment, mount, coin	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		B. Holm	
229 Lõmala	C	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Penannular brooch, chain holder, fastening plate, fragment of bracelet, fragment of pendant, head dress	12th–13th cc	SM 10908	K. Treimann	
230 Läägisoo	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Hammer, wedge, rectangular ornament link, finger-ring, nails, boat rivet, coin, metal items	Middle Ages		Anonymous	

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231	Lümanda	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Rectangular ornament link, small round brooch, coins, silver coin fragment, nails, chain holder, belt end, brooch pins, coin pendants, bell with chain fragment, tobacco pipe cleaner, pendant fragment, metal item	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Tohv, K. Laane	
232	Meedla	S?	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Penannular brooch, small ring brooch, axe	Viking – Middle Ages		E. Kessel	Ü. Tamla, M.-L. Posti
233	Mullutu	HS	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Mount fragment, finger-ring fragment, buckle, rectangular ornament link, finger-ring, brooch pin, coin pendant	Late Iron Age		T. Tohv	
234	Tahula	C, S?	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Rectangular ornament link, mount, finger-ring, mounts, tweezers, hook, cruciform pendant, fragment of silver bead, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		P. E. Mustonen	
235	Tammese	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Stone axe fragment	Late Neolithic – Bronze Age		Anonymous	
236	Upa	C	Saaremaa (Kaarma)	Rectangular ornament link, trapezoid pendant, fragment of dress pin head, burnt fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age		P. E. Mustonen	
237	Vaivere	F	Saaremaa (Püha)	Fragment of silver bracelet, rectangular ornament link, fragment of copper alloy jewellery	Final Iron Age		P. E. Mustonen	
238	Varpe	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Penannular brooch, tweezers, mount, pewter pendant and fragments, finger-ring fragment, ring fragment, scale weights, copper alloy bar, metal items	Late Iron Age, Modern Period		T. Tohv, K. Laane	
239	Veeriku	C?	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Agraffe button	Migration Period		M. Avamere	
240	Viira	F	Saaremaa (Karja)	Flanged axe	Early Bronze Age		Anonymous	K. Paavel
241	Väike-Rahula	F	Saaremaa (Pöide)	Fragment of sword	Iron Age?		M. Porovart	

TARTUMAA

242	Alasoo	H, F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Coins, spearhead, pottery	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		V. Vulf	
243	Järiste	S	Nõo	Axe, nail	Final Iron Age	TÜ 3019	E. Jegorov	M. Kaseorg
244	Kardla	C?, S	Tartu town (Nõo)	Ice nail, buckles, bell, rings, coins, mount, signet rings, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooch, dress pin, needle, burnt items)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		P. Laidre, I. Kiudorf	S. Jegorov

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245	Elva municipality	H	Elva (Nõo)	Bracteates, wheel thrown pottery	13th–14th cc		Anonymous	M. Kiudsoo
246	Kurista	F	Kastre (Võnnu)	Mace head?	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
247	Lammiku	F	Tartu (Äksi)	Zoomorphic fastening plate	Final Iron Age		P. Laidre	S. Jegorov
248	Nina	C, S, F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Finger-ring, orthodox cruciform pendants, pewter seal, pipe tobacco cleaner, buttons, bell fragment, metal items	Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
249	Piiri	C, S, F	Tartu (Räpina)	Small round brooch, finger-rings, signet ring, mount, belt fitting, bell, coins, buckle, orthodox cruci- form pendants, button, axe, fragments of copper alloy items, pottery	Middle Ages – Modern Period		S. Kürsa, I. Tsakuhhin	
250	Praaga	C, S, F	Peipsiääre (Võnnu)	Orthodox cruciform pendant, bullets, fragment of horse shoe, nail, mount, fastening plates with ring, other fragments	Modern Period		A. Kotkin, S. Kürsa	
251	Saare	C, S, F	Tartu (Räpina)	Signet rings, orthodox cruciform pendants, coins, dirham, buttons, fin- ger-rings, nail, signet rings, key, mount, pendants, buckles, bells, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. small round brooch), metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Kotkin, S. Kürsa	
252	Tooni	C, S, F	Tartu (Räpina)	Finger-rings, signet rings, buckles, buckle pin, tin bullets, coins, buttons, small round brooch, cruci- form pendant, fragments of copper alloy jewellery	Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
253	Tähtvere	F	Tartu town (Nõo)	Penannular brooch, frag- ment of bracelet	Final Iron Age		A. Kotkin	
254	Varnja	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Finger-rings, signet ring, bells, lock detail, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooch, coin, orthodox cruciform pen- dants), round item	Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
255	Voika	C	Nõo	Penannular brooch, rectan- gular ornament link, bell, finger-ring, mount, coins, fragments of brooch pins and finger ring	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Jegorov	
256	Voika	S	Nõo	Pendant, buckle, dirham, coin pendants, penannular brooch, finger-ring with volute, fragment of brace- let, fragment of dress pin, signet ring, finger-ring, coin fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Jegorov	

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VALGAMAA							
257 Kalliküla	F	Valga (Hargla)	Flint scraper	Stone Age?		J. Hass	
258 Kiviküla	C	Valga (Sangaste)	Fragments of spindle whorl, signet rings, coins, book clasp, bell, fragments of copper alloy items (penannular brooch, round brooches, dress pin, mount, burnt items)	Modern Period		Anonymous	
259 Koobassaare	F	Valga (Karula)	Bronze socketed axe, finger-ring, thimble, fragments of finger-ring and copper alloy item	Late Bronze Age, Middle Ages – Modern Period		I. Tsakuhhin	
260 Vaalu	C, S	Otepää (Sangaste)	Mount, finger-ring, signet rings, bell, coin pendants, axe, fragment of tripod pot?, burnt items, spindle whorl, coins, small round brooch, tin item	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
261 Väljaküla	F	Valga (Sangaste)	Finger-ring, fragment of signet ring, fragments of ornamented copper alloy items			Anonymous	
262 Õlatu	F	Valga (Sangaste)	Penannular brooch, fragments of ornamented copper alloy jewellery, tin mount	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Erik	
VILJANDIMAA							
263 Karksi	S	Mulgi (Karksi)	Coins, finger-rings, mounts, brooch pins, small round brooch, cloth seals, fragments of copper alloy items (signet ring, buckle, bracelet, belt separator, other items), tin dice(?), tin figurine, fragments of tin figurines, fragments of spur	Modern Period		Anonymous	R.-M. Moon
264 Kulla	F	Mulgi (Halliste)	Mace head	Final Iron Age?		Anonymous	
265 Marjamäe	F	Viljandi (Tarvastu)	Pewter pendant	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		R. Olde	
266 Sooviku	S	Viljandi (Tarvastu)	Coin, finger-ring, fragment of belt fitting, mount, candlestick, fragment of gun iron, tin bullets, other tin and iron fragments	Modern Period		A. Kotkin	
267 Suislepa	F	Viljandi (Tarvastu)	Stone axe	Late Neolithic – Bronze Age		Anonymous	
268 Sürgavere	S	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Iron bloom, pendants, bells, mounts, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. buckle, bracelets, burnt items)	Iron Age – Middle Ages		R. Ots	
269 Sürgavere	F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Fragment of zoomorphic pendant, tin button	Final Iron Age		R. Ots	

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VÕRUMAA								
270	Oe	S	Antsla (Urvaste)	Penannular brooches, chalcidony bead, mounts, bells, pendant, piece of flint, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. finger-ring)	Modern Period		J. Naaber	
271	Popovitsa	F	Setomaa	Orthodox pendant, finger-ring, metal item, round ornamented item	Modern Period		S. Kürsa	
272	Uhtjärve	C, S	Antsla (Urvaste)	Small round brooch, fastening plates, cruciform pendant, pendant with volute, fragments of copper alloy items (scabbard chape, buckle, penannular brooch)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		J. Naaber	
273	Vaabina	C, S	Antsla (Urvaste)	Mount, bells, pendants, penannular brooches, buckle, pin, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. round brooches, bracelets, burnt items), fragments of dirhams	Viking Age – Modern Period		J. Naaber	
274	Vastseliina	F	Võru (Vastseliina)	Mount, fragment of mount	Final Iron Age		A. Samarin	

REFERENCES

- Almgren, O. 2013.** Studien über nordeuropäische Fibelformen der ersten nachchristlichen Jahrhunderte mit Berücksichtigung der provinzialrömischen und südrussischen Formen, 2nd ed. Leipzig.
- Asplund, H. 2005.** The bear and the female. Bear-tooth pendants in Late Iron Age Finland. – Rituals and relations. Studies on the Society and Material Culture of the Baltic Finns. Ed. by S. Mäntylä. Suomalaisen Tiedeakatemia toimituksia: Humaniora 336. Helsinki, 13–30.
- Hauptmann, T. 1998.** Studien zu den Dreispissenfibeln. – 100 Jahre Fibelformen nach Oscar Almgren: Internationale Arbeitstagung 25.–28.05.1997, Kleinmachnow, Land Brandenburg. Ed. by J. Kunow. Forschungen zur Archäologie im Land Brandenburg, 5. Wünsdorf, 159–173.
- HCA amendment 2011** = Amendments to the Heritage Conservation Act. Riigi Teataja I 21.03.2011, 28. <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/121032011008>
- Jegorov, S. 2022.** Rauatoorikute ja šlakide päritoluanalüüs. Tartu. (*Manuscript in TŪAK.*)
- Jonuks, T. 2017.** Bronze Tooth Pendants from the Late Iron Age: Between Real and Fictional Zooarchaeology. – Norwegian Archaeological Review, 50: 2, 135–148.
- Kangert, N. & Varul, L. 2022.** Lõmala neiu – muinasäegne luustik Lääne-Saaremaal. – Muinsuskaitse aastaraamat 2021, 87.
- Kiudsoo, M. 2022.** Keskaegne mündiaare Elva vallast. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Kiudsoo, M., Tamla, Ü. & Vinkler, R. 2012.** Ornaments of Finnish origin from Partsaare. – AVE, 2011, 237–244.
- Kivikoski, E. 1938.** Likarmade spännen från vikingatiden. – Finskt Museum XLV. Helsingfors, 10–26.
- Kivikoski, E. 1973.** Die Eisenzeit Finnlands. Bildwerk und Text. Neuauflage. Helsinki.
- Kivisalo, N. 2008.** The Late Iron Age Bear-Tooth Pendants in Finland: Symbolic Mediators between Women, Bears, and Wilderness? – Temenos 44: 2, 263–291.
- Kurisoo, T. 2021.** Adornment, self-definition, religion: Pendants of the north-eastern Baltic Sea region, 9th–13th century. *Studien zur Siedlungsgeschichte und Archäologie der Ostseegebiete, Bd. 19.* Kiel-Hamburg.
- Kurisoo, T., Rammo, R. & Smirnova, M. 2020.** Discoveries made by the users of searching devices and the public in 2019 and the new Heritage Conservation Act. – AVE, 2019, 263–288.
- Kurisoo, T., Rammo, R., Smirnova, M. & Kangert, N. 2021.** Searching devices, new discoveries, and issues related to them in Estonian archaeology in 2020. – AVE, 2020, 265–291.
- Leimus, I. 2021a.** Ontika aardeleiu ekspertiishinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Leimus, I. 2021b.** Ekspertarvamus Virumaal Lügenuse vallas Vainu külas avastatud 10. sajandi mündiaarde kohta. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Leimus, I. 2021c.** Ekspertiis Ida-Virumaalt Erra alevikust leitud müntide kohta. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Leimus, I. 2021d.** Ekspertiis Lääne maakonnas Kirimäe külas avastatud aardeleiu kohta. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Mägi, M. 2020.** Before the hill fort of Valjala was built. Landing places and graves along the Lõve River in Saaremaa. – AVE, 2019, 69–78.
- Mandel, M. 2021.** Võhma (Uluste?) põletuskalmistu. Ekspertihinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Muinsuskaitseamet. 2021.** Arheoloogilise leiu üleandmise-vastuvõtmise akt nr 5.1-15/257. Tallinn. (*Document in MA.*)
- Ots, M. & Rammo, R. 2013.** Landscape surveys and new monuments discovered in 2012. – AVE, 2012, 297–319.
- Paavel, K. 2021.** Pronkskirves Muhu saarelt Viira külast. Ekspertihinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Rammo, R. & Kangert, N. 2018.** Discoveries made by users of searching devices and the public in 2017. – AVE, 2017, 207–224.
- Rammo, R. & Smirnova, M. 2019.** Discoveries made by users of searching devices and the public in 2018. – AVE, 2018, 263–282.
- Roio, M. 2022.** Tulekivist esemed Jõgevamaalt Jõgeva vallast Laiusevälja külast Altveski kinnistult. Ekspertihinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Russow, E. 2021a.** Metallese Lääne-Virumaalt Veltsi külast Jaani katastriüksuselt (66201:001:0884). Ekspertihinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Russow, E. 2021b.** Naast Pärnumaalt Tori vallast Eametsa külast (KÜ 73001:001:0153). Ekspertihinnang. Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Russow, E. 2021c.** Erandlik leid Läänemaalt – keskaegne ehisbrakteat Erja külast. – Läänemaa muuseumi toimetised, 23, 113–131.
- Russow, E. 2021d.** Keskaegne pitsat Jõgevamaalt Selli külast (KÜ 24801:001:1650). Tallinn. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Russow, E. 2022.** Laar või metsmees Raplamaalt? Tutulus: Eesti arheoloogia aastakiri, 2021, 4–5.
- Saage, R. 2022.** Ekspertihinnang sepistamisega seotud leidudest Lümandust. Tartu. (*Manuscript in MA.*)
- Tamla, Ü. & Kiudsoo, M. 2017.** Soomevere silver hoard. – AVE, 2016, 69–74.
- Tvauri, A. 2017.** Three medieval and early modern hoards from Pugritsa village, historical Võrumaa. – AVE, 2016, 81–92.

2021. AASTA DETEKTORI- JA JUHULEIUD NING ANDMETE HALDAMISEGA SEOTUD VÄLJAKUTSED

Tuuli Kurisoo, Mari-Liis Posti, Nele Kangert ja Krista Karro

Artikkel annab esmalt ülevaate 2021. aasta jooksul Muinsuskaitseametisse (MA) jõudnud detektori- ja juhuleidudest. Lisaks käsitletakse nende esemete seotud probleeme ja väljakutseid MA vaates. Arheoloogiliste leidude ja leiukohtade ülevaade põhineb tabelis 1 esitatud informatsioonil (jn 1), suur osa nendest määrangutest on esialgsed ja võivad hiljem muutuda. Tabelist on välja jäetud leiud, mida ei õnnestunud määrata ning leiukogumid, mis koosnevad 19.–20. saj esemetest.

Sarnaselt eelmistele aastatele on rohkem leiukohti teada põhjapoolsest Eestist (tabel 1, jn 1). Eraldi tasub välja tuua, et Järvamaa ja Lääne-Virumaa on muutunud otsinguvahendi kasutajate meelispiirkondadeks Harjumaa järel. Ida-Virumaa ja Raplamaa andmed on varasemate aastatega sarnased. Leiti mitmeid uusi aardeid (nt nr 57, 69, 79, 88, 126, 160, 185), igast vaatluse all olnud maakonnast on vihjeid ka erinevate matusepaikade kohta (nt nr 6, 11, 34, 75, 77, 115, 135, 166, 210, 211) ning võib arvata, et üsna mitmed leiukogumid on seotud asulakohadega (nt nr 3, 18, 110, 116, 141, 174, 213). Kõige vanemad leiud on pronksiaegsed putkkirved Keilast (nr 13), Errast (nr 67) ja Seliküläst (nr 134). Mitmed leiukogumid sisaldavad vanema rauaaja esemeid (nt nr 51, 57, 76, 84, 85, 113, 125, 133, 152, 158), millest kõige haruldasem on Saka (nr 85) matusepaigast pärit kärbissõlg (jn 2). Tegu on rooma rauaage seiuiga, mis on ühtlasi vanim kärbissõle tüüp (Almgreni tüüp 95), mis tõenäoliselt jõudis Eestisse Poola aladelt. Otsinguvahendi kasutamine on juurde toonud ka mitmeid võrdõlgseid sõlgi, 2021. aasta andmestikust on neid kaks, Jalalõpest (nr 111) ja Metstagusest (nr 128).

Veel saadi põhjapoolsest Eestist viis noorema rauaaja aardeleidu, millest kõige haruldasem on 8. sajandi lõppu dateeritav Vitsiku aare. Ontika (nr 79). Vainu (nr 88) ja Erra (nr 69) on veidi nooremad, aga samamoodi olulised numismaatilised allikad. Valingu (nr 57) aare koosneb ilmselt hakkõbedana hoiul olnud 11. sajandi hoburaudsõlgede katketest. Noorema rauaaja esemed on võrdlemisi arvukad, kuid laialt levinud esemetüübid. Teistest erilisem ese, vasesulamist kihvakujuline ripats, saadi Saulast (nr 46). Sellised kihvipatsid olid eelkõige kasutusel Edela-Soomes, vähesel hulgal ka liivlaste juures. Keska- ja uusaegsetest esemetest tasub esile tõsta keskaegses Euroopas tuntud mütoloogilist metsmehe kujukest Äherdist (nr 215; jn 3) ja Veltsi miniatuursest uhmri- nia (nr 183), mida võidi kasutada mängumajakomp-

lektis hariduslikul eesmärgil. Lümandast saadud rauast esemed (jn 4 B–E) viitavad 14.–17. saj tegutsenud sepikojale, kusjuures esmakordne on rauast toru, mis oma teostusviisilt sobib kõige paremini lõõtsa otsa käivaks lõõrikuks (jn 4: B). Hobiootsijate panuse läbi on märgatavalt kasvanud ka 16.–17. saj aardeleidude osakaal, millest ehteasjade hulga ja kvaliteedi poolest on üks silmapaistvamaid Vetiku (Mõdriku, nr 185) aare.

Läänepoolsest Eestist on teavet märgatavalt vähem. Kõige rohkem anti teada otsinguvahendi abil saadud leidudest Saaremaal (26 leiukohta), millele järgneb Pärnumaa 14 leiukohaga. Vaid seitse teadet on Läänemaalt, kuid esile tasub tõsta Hiiumaa kolme leiupaika, mis annavad uut informatsiooni asustusaajaloo kohta. Pooli leiupaikadest saab seostada mõne muistisega, mille hulgas domineerivad asulakohad (nt nr 145, 194, 217, 224, 226, 230, 238) ja matusepaigad (nt nr 147, 206, 221, 229, 236). Aardeid leiti kaks, millest muinasaja lõppu dateeritav Kirimäe (nr 144) sisaldab ka tõeliselt haruldasi münte. Leiumateterjali hulgas oli vanimaks esemeks tõenäoliselt kiviaja lõpust pärinev kivikirves (nr 235). Kogu andmestiku vanim metallese, varase pronksiaja kirves, pärineb Viira (nr 240) küläst, mis kurioosselt oli kasutusel riidenagina, enne kui selles tunti ära arheoloogiline leid.

Suur hulk leide pärineb muinasaja lõpusajanditest ja nende hulgas on üheks tähtsamaks avastuseks Lõmala (nr 229) matus. Hobiootsijad, kes selle avastuse tegid, käitusid eeskujulikult ning teavitasid MA-d kohe 12.–13. saj ehtekatketest ning kolju fragmendi leidmisest. Arheoloogilistel kaevamistel sai selgeks, et maetu oli 15–19-aastane noor naine, kelle suririie juures olid mitmeid ehteleidu, millest kõige silmapaistvam on peakate (jn 5). Ka kesk- ja uusaegsed leiud on arvukad, millest mainimist vääri- vad eelkõige kaks eset – keskaegne ehiskatkeaat Eametsast (nr 194) ning esimene metallist valuvormi katke, mis on pärit arheoloogilisest kontekstist (nr 219).

Teave lõunapoolse Eesti kohta on pigem napp võrreldes põhjapoolse Eestiga, aga sarnane varasematele aastatele. Jõgevamaa (16 leiukohaga) ja Tartumaa (15 leiukohaga) on kõige populaarsemad maakonnad otsinguvahendite kasutajate seas. Teiste maakondade leiukohade arv on alla kümne: Viljandi (7 leiukohta), Valga (6 leiukohta), Võru (5 leiukohta), Põlva (4 leiukohta). Juhuleiud on kõige arvukamad (nt nr 97, 104, 106, 191, 246, 257, 259, 264, 265, 267, 271, 274), kuid tundub, et üsna palju informatsiooni on ka matuse-

paikade kohta (nr 93, 95, 98, 101, 103, 258, 260, 273). Aardeleidudest väärrib märkimist Elva vallast (nr 245) aiatööde käigus avastatud aare, mis koosneb tuhandetest 13.–14. saj müntidest. Mitmed leiupaigad Tartu- ja Põlvamaalt on seotud jätkuva otsingutegevusega Peipsi järve äärsetel aladel (nt nr 191–193, 248–250, 252).

Lõunapoolse Eesti vanimad esemeleidud on kivi- aegne tulekivist kõõvits Kalliküläst (nr 257), Suislepa (nr 276) kivikirves neoliitikumi lõpust või pronksi- ajast Koobassaare (nr 259) pronksiaegne putkkirves. Ülejäänud leidude seas on rohkesti muinasaja lõpust uusajani dateeritavaid esemeid ning nende hulgas domineerivad erinevad ehte- ja rõivaste detailid, kuid on ka paar haruldasemat avastust. Marjamäe (nr 265) külast saadi näokujutisega võreripats, kus- juures antropomorfseid esemeid on arheoloogiliste leidude seas väga harva. Väljapaistvaks esemeks on 13.–14. saj dateeringuga pitsat Sellist (nr 103). Pitsati servaalal on tekst S'HERMANNI DE PAI'SGELE ehk pitsat, mille omanik oli tõenäoliselt Pai'sgelest pärit Hermanninimeline vasall (jn 6). Veel tasub maini- mist Sürgavere (nr 268) massiivne rauatoorik (3,4 kg;

jn 3: A). Esiialgse analüüsi tulemusel on tegemist Viljandimaal toodetud rauaga, kuna rauatooriku sees olev šlakk on sarnase koostisega Sürgaverele lähedal asuvale Olustvere šlakile.

Viimase teemana on artiklis vaatluse all metalli- detektoriga saadud leidude haldamine ning sellega seotud probleematika. Viimase kümne aasta jook- sul on hobiotsijate arv kasvanud hüppeliselt 91 loa- omanikust (2012) ligi 800 loaomanikuni (2021). Seega on märkimisväärselt suurenenud leidude hulk ning uute muististe arv. Ressursi nappus MA-s on teinud süsteemi haldamise, aga ka leidude konserveerimise ning uue mälestiste kaitse alla võtmise keeruliseks. Tasub mainida, et mitte ühtki hiljuti mälestiseks tunnistatud muistist ei ole leidnud hobiotsijad, kuigi nad on avastanud kõige enam uusi muistiseid. Siiski on toimunud ka mõned positiivsed arengud. Alates 2021. aastast on MA-s kaks töökohta hobiotsijate lei- dudega tegelemiseks ning olulise panuse on andnud teadusprojekti MetDect andmebaasi integreerimine MA töövahendite hulka. MetDecti andmebaasis olev informatsioon võimaldab tuvastada uusi muistiseid, aga on ka oluline tööriist ennetustegevuseks.